

ISic1422

I.Sicily inscription 1422

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Kasmenai

Place of origin (modern)

near Chiaramonte Gulfi

Provenance

Monte Casale

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 49214

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333361

1. [— —] εἰ Ῥαχὸ⁻²⁷Ῥαψὸ⁻²⁷ [— —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644972

EDCS 71000255

PHI 333361

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 46.1260.3

Manganaro, G. 1996. Studi di epigrafia siceliota. *Rendiconti dell'Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Classe di Scienze morali, storiche e filologiche*. 9.7: 27-63. At 63 fig.27

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